

Supplementary documents: Scoping Review

Authors	Title
Hung et al. (2022)	8-b Precision 8-Mb ReRAM Compute-in-Memory Macro Using Direct-Current-Free Time-Domain Readout Scheme for AI Edge Devices
Konstantakopoulos et al. (2019)	A deep learning and gamification approach to improving human-building interaction and energy efficiency in smart infrastructure
Mozo et al. (2023)	A Machine-Learning-Based Cyberattack Detector for a Cloud-Based SDN Controller
Jayashankara et al. (2023)	A Novel Approach for Short-Term Energy Forecasting in Smart Buildings
Y. Wang et al. (2023)	An Energy-Efficient Transformer Processor Exploiting Dynamic Weak Relevances in Global Attention
Choi and Kim (2020)	An on-device deep learning approach to battery saving on industrial mobile terminals
Roy et al. (2019)	Ant-Lion Optimizer algorithm and recurrent neural network for energy management of micro grid connected system
Zhao et al. (2023)	ARBiS: A Hardware-Efficient SRAM CIM CNN Accelerator with Cyclic-Shift Weight Duplication and Parasitic-Capacitance Charge Sharing for AI Edge Application
Hazarika et al. (2022)	Area and energy efficient shift and accumulator unit for object detection in IoT applications
Haider and Ko (2023)	Booth Encoding-Based Energy Efficient Multipliers for Deep Learning Systems
Liu et al. (2022)	Collaborative Edge Computing with FPGA-Based CNN Accelerators for Energy-Efficient and Time-Aware Face Tracking System
Xin et al. (2017)	COSY: An energy-efficient hardware architecture for deep convolutional neural networks based on systolic array
Sun (2024)	DMFF: Deep multimodel feature fusion for building occupancy detection
Z. Wang et al. (2024)	EDCompress: Energy-Aware Model Compression for Dataflows
Mohapatra et al. (2022)	Energy Consumption Prediction in Electrical Appliances of Commercial Buildings Using LSTM-GRU Model
Zawish et al. (2023)	Energy-Aware AI-Driven Framework for Edge-Computing-Based IoT Applications
Frey et al. (2022)	Energy-aware neural architecture selection and hyperparameter optimization
Mukherjee et al. (2021)	Energy-efficient resource allocation strategy in massive iot for industrial 6G applications
Y.-H. Chen et al. (2016)	Eyeriss: A Spatial Architecture for Energy-Efficient Dataflow for Convolutional Neural Networks
Saptalakar and Latte (2023)	FPGA-based reflection image removal using cognitive neural networks
Zeng et al. (2023)	GreenPLM: Cross-Lingual Transfer of Monolingual Pre-Trained Language Models at Almost No Cost
Akbarzadeh et al. (2024)	Heating-Cooling Monitoring and Power Consumption Forecasting Using LSTM for Energy-Efficient Smart Management of Buildings: A Computational Intelligence Solution for Smart Homes
Iftikhar et al. (2023)	HunterPlus: AI based energy-efficient task scheduling for cloud-fog computing environments
Fouad et al. (2020)	Machine learning and IoT for smart grid
Trabelsi Ajili and Hara-Azumi (2022)	Multimodal Neural Network Acceleration on a Hybrid CPU-FPGA Architecture: A Case Study
Komala et al. (2023)	Multi-UAV computing enabling efficient clustering-based IoT for energy reduction and data transmission
Kaiser et al. (2023)	Neuromorphic-P2M: processing-in-pixel-in-memory paradigm for neuromorphic image sensors
Sumathi et al. (2022)	NEWTR: a multipath routing for next hop destination in internet of things with artificial recurrent neural network (RNN)
Junaid et al. (2022)	Optimal Architecture of Floating-Point Arithmetic for Neural Network Training Processors
Deng et al. (2021)	PermCNN: Energy-Efficient Convolutional Neural Network Hardware Architecture with Permuted Diagonal Structure

Rahman et al. (2018)	Predicting electricity consumption for commercial and residential buildings using deep recurrent neural networks
Escorcia-Gutierrez et al. (2024)	Privacy Preserving Blockchain with Energy Aware Clustering Scheme for IoT Healthcare Systems
Zhu et al. (2022)	Research on A Chiplet-based DSA (Domain-Specific Architectures) Scalable Convolutional Acceleration Architecture
Li et al. (2024)	Research on key technologies of high energy efficiency and low power consumption of new data acquisition equipment of power Internet of Things based on artificial intelligence
Y. Chen et al. (2019)	Robust and energy-efficient expression recognition based on improved deep ResNets
Barbierato and Gatti (2024)	Toward Green AI: A Methodological Survey of the Scientific Literature

References

- Akbarzadeh, O., Hamzehei, S., Attar, H., Amer, A., Fasihour, N., Khosravi, M. R., & Solyman, A. A. (2024). Heating-Cooling Monitoring and Power Consumption Forecasting Using LSTM for Energy-Efficient Smart Management of Buildings: A Computational Intelligence Solution for Smart Homes. *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, 29(1), 143–157. <https://doi.org/10.26599/TST.2023.9010008>
- Barbierato, E., & Gatti, A. (2024). Toward Green AI: A Methodological Survey of the Scientific Literature. *IEEE Access*, 12, 23989–24013. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3360705>
- Chen, Y.-H., Emer, J., & Sze, V. (2016). Eyeriss: A Spatial Architecture for Energy-Efficient Dataflow for Convolutional Neural Networks. *Proceedings - 2016 43rd International Symposium on Computer Architecture, ISCA 2016*, 367–379. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCA.2016.40>
- Chen, Y., Du, J., Liu, Q., Zhang, L., & Zeng, Y. (2019). Robust and energy-efficient expression recognition based on improved deep ResNets. *Biomedizinische Technik*, 64(5), 519–528. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bmt-2018-0027>
- Choi, I., & Kim, H. (2020). An on-device deep learning approach to battery saving on industrial mobile terminals. *Sensors (Switzerland)*, 20(14), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20144044>
- Deng, C., Liao, S., & Yuan, B. (2021). PermCNN: Energy-Efficient Convolutional Neural Network Hardware Architecture with Permuted Diagonal Structure. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 70(2), 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TC.2020.2981068>
- Escorcía-Gutiérrez, J., Mansour, R. F., Leal, E., Villanueva, J., Jiménez-Cabas, J., Soto, C., & Soto-Díaz, R. (2024). Privacy Preserving Blockchain with Energy Aware Clustering Scheme for IoT Healthcare Systems. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 29(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-023-02115-9>
- Fouad, M., Mali, R., Lmouatassime, A., & Bousmah, P. R. M. (2020). Machine learning and IoT for smart grid. In K. I.R., B. A. M., B. A.A., & A. B.K. (Eds.), *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives (Vol. 44, Issue 4/W3, pp. 233–240)*. International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIV-4-W3-2020-233-2020>
- Frey, N. C., Zhao, D., Axelrod, S., Jones, M., Bestor, D., Gadepally, V., Gomez-Bombarelli, R., & Samsi, S. (2022). Energy-aware neural architecture selection and hyperparameter optimization. *Proceedings - 2022 IEEE 36th International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium Workshops, IPDPSW 2022*, 732–741. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPSW55747.2022.00125>
- Haider, M. H., & Ko, S.-B. (2023). Booth Encoding-Based Energy Efficient Multipliers for Deep Learning Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, 70(6), 2241–2245. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSII.2022.3233923>
- Hazarika, A., Poddar, S., Nasralla, M. M., & Rahaman, H. (2022). Area and energy efficient shift and accumulator unit for object detection in IoT applications. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 61(1), 795–809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2021.04.099>
- Hung, J., Wen, T., Huang, Y., Huang, S., Chang, F., Su, C., Khwa, W., Lo, C., Liu, R., Hsieh, C., Tang, K., Chih, Y., Chang, T. J., & Chang, M. (2022). 8-b Precision 8-Mb ReRAM Compute-in-Memory Macro Using Direct-Current-Free Time-Domain Readout Scheme for AI Edge Devices. *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSSC.2022.3200515>

- Iftikhar, S., Ahmad, M. M. M., Tuli, S., Chowdhury, D., Xu, M., Gill, S. S., & Uhlig, S. (2023). HunterPlus: AI based energy-efficient task scheduling for cloud–fog computing environments. *Internet of Things (Netherlands)*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2022.100667>
- Jayashankara, M., Shah, P., Sharma, A., Chanak, P., & Singh, S. K. (2023). A Novel Approach for Short-Term Energy Forecasting in Smart Buildings. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 23(5), 5307–5314. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2023.3237876>
- Junaid, M., Arslan, S., Lee, T., & Kim, H. (2022). Optimal Architecture of Floating-Point Arithmetic for Neural Network Training Processors. *Sensors*, 22(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22031230>
- Kaiser, M. A.-A., Datta, G., Wang, Z., Jacob, A. P., Beerel, P. A., & Jaiswal, A. R. (2023). Neuromorphic-P2M: processing-in-pixel-in-memory paradigm for neuromorphic image sensors. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2023.1144301>
- Komala, C. R., Velmurugan, V., Maheswari, K., Deena, S., Kavitha, M., & Rajaram, A. (2023). Multi-UAV computing enabling efficient clustering-based IoT for energy reduction and data transmission. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 45(1), 1717–1730. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-231242>
- Konstantakopoulos, I. C., Barkan, A. R., He, S., Veeravalli, T., Liu, H., & Spanos, C. (2019). A deep learning and gamification approach to improving human-building interaction and energy efficiency in smart infrastructure. *Applied Energy*, 237, 810–821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.12.065>
- Li, X., Zhao, H., Feng, Y., Li, J., Zhao, Y., & Wang, X. (2024). Research on key technologies of high energy efficiency and low power consumption of new data acquisition equipment of power Internet of Things based on artificial intelligence. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2024.100575>
- Liu, X., Yang, J., Zou, C., Chen, Q., Yan, X., Chen, Y., & Cai, C. (2022). Collaborative Edge Computing with FPGA-Based CNN Accelerators for Energy-Efficient and Time-Aware Face Tracking System. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 9(1), 252–266. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSS.2021.3059318>
- Mohapatra, S. K., Mishra, S., & Tripathy, H. K. (2022). Energy Consumption Prediction in Electrical Appliances of Commercial Buildings Using LSTM-GRU Model. In M. J.R., T. H.K., M. S.K., M. S., & S. K.S. (Eds.), *ASSIC 2022 - Proceedings: International Conference on Advancements in Smart, Secure and Intelligent Computing*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASSIC55218.2022.10088334>
- Mozo, A., Karamchandani, A., de la Cal, L., Gómez-Canaval, S., Pastor, A., & Gifre, L. (2023). A Machine-Learning-Based Cyberattack Detector for a Cloud-Based SDN Controller. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 13(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13084914>
- Mukherjee, A., Goswami, P., Khan, M. A., Manman, L., Yang, L., & Pillai, P. (2021). Energy-efficient resource allocation strategy in massive iot for industrial 6G applications. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 8(7), 5194–5201. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.3035608>
- Rahman, A., Srikumar, V., & Smith, A. D. (2018). Predicting electricity consumption for commercial and residential buildings using deep recurrent neural networks. *Applied Energy*, 212, 372–385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.12.051>
- Roy, K., Mandal, K. K., & Mandal, A. C. (2019). Ant-Lion Optimizer algorithm and recurrent neural network for energy management of micro grid connected system. *Energy*, 167, 402–416.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.10.153>

- Saptalakar, B. K., & Latte, M. V. (2023). FPGA-based reflection image removal using cognitive neural networks. *Applied Nanoscience (Switzerland)*, *13*(3), 2539–2553. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13204-022-02352-6>
- Sumathi, A. C., Javadpour, A., Pinto, P., Sangaiah, A. K., Zhang, W., & Mahmoodi Khaniabadi, S. (2022). NEWTR: a multipath routing for next hop destination in internet of things with artificial recurrent neural network (RNN). *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, *13*(10), 2869–2889. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-022-01568-w>
- Sun, K. (2024). DMFF: Deep multimodel feature fusion for building occupancy detection. *Building and Environment*, *253*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111355>
- Trabelsi Ajili, M., & Hara-Azumi, Y. (2022). Multimodal Neural Network Acceleration on a Hybrid CPU-FPGA Architecture: A Case Study. *IEEE Access*, *10*, 9603–9617. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3144977>
- Wang, Y., Qin, Y., Deng, D., Wei, J., Zhou, Y., Fan, Y., Chen, T., Sun, H., Liu, L., Wei, S., & Yin, S. (2023). An Energy-Efficient Transformer Processor Exploiting Dynamic Weak Relevances in Global Attention. *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, *58*(1), 227–242. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSSC.2022.3213521>
- Wang, Z., Luo, T., Goh, R. S. M., & Zhou, J. T. (2024). EDCompress: Energy-Aware Model Compression for Dataflows. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, *35*(1), 208–220. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2022.3172941>
- Xin, C., Chen, Q., Tian, M., Ji, M., Zou, C., Wang, X., & Wang, B. (2017). COSY: An energy-efficient hardware architecture for deep convolutional neural networks based on systolic array. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems - ICPADS, 2017-Decem*, 180–189. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPADS.2017.00034>
- Zawish, M., Ashraf, N., Ansari, R. I., & Davy, S. (2023). Energy-Aware AI-Driven Framework for Edge-Computing-Based IoT Applications. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *10*(6), 5013–5023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2022.3219202>
- Zeng, Q., Garay, L., Zhou, P., Chong, D., Hua, Y., Wu, J., Pan, Y., Zhou, H., Voigt, R., & Yang, J. (2023). GreenPLM: Cross-Lingual Transfer of Monolingual Pre-Trained Language Models at Almost No Cost. In E. E. (Ed.), *IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vols. 2023-Augus, pp. 6290–6298)*. International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85170386241&partnerID=40&md5=ac72d6620d0443d1d4c35ac87884abe4>
- Zhao, C., Fang, J., Jiang, J., Xue, X., & Zeng, X. (2023). ARBiS: A Hardware-Efficient SRAM CIM CNN Accelerator with Cyclic-Shift Weight Duplication and Parasitic-Capacitance Charge Sharing for AI Edge Application. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, *70*(1), 364–377. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2022.3215535>
- Zhu, S., Miao, M., Zhang, Z., & Duan, X. (2022). Research on A Chiplet-based DSA (Domain-Specific Architectures) Scalable Convolutional Acceleration Architecture. *2022 23rd International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology, ICEPT 2022*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEPT56209.2022.9873177>